

Impact Factor: 5.479

ISSN 2181-9505

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9505

Philosophy and Life

FALSAFA VA HAYOT • ФИЛОСОФИЯ И ЖИЗНЬ

Special
Issue 2

2023

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI VAZIRLAR MAHKAMASI
HUZURIDAGI IMOM BUXORIY XALQARO
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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 2

PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 2

Jurnal bir yilda 4
marta nashr qilinadi.

Журнал выходит
4 раза в год.

The journal is published
4 times in a year.

ISSN: 2181-9505
DOI: 10.26739/2181-9505

2023

FALSAFA VA HAYOT XALQARO JURNAL

№SI-2 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9505-2023-SI-2>

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Решением Высшей аттестационной комиссии при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан введен в список специальных журналов. 2018 год 29 декабря протокол №260/7

Регистрационное свидетельство №1175 выдано 27.02.2018 агенством по печати и информации Узбекистана

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The registration certificate № 1175 was issued on February 27, 2018 by the Uzbek Agency for Press and Information

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EDUCATION AS IMPARTIAL PART OF INTELLIGENCE

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330666>

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to philosophical analysis of education and its comparison with intelligence. Among the various situations in the relationship of intelligence and education, there are analytical cases that characterize definition, its specific philosophical environment. This study, in turn, determines the axiological analysis of intelligentsia and education, specific features of these two terminologies.

The ideas of education and intelligence are characterized in the example of the teacher, who as a model can be educated but not always this characteristics comes simultaneously with intelligence.

Keywords: intelligence, educated person, intellectual maturity, relations, ethical environment, conservative period, school, teacher.

Бурханова Маъмура Гулямовна
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ОБРАЗОВАННОСТЬ КАК НЕОТЪЕМЛЕМАЯ ЧАСТЬ ИНТЕЛЛИГЕНТНОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена философскому анализу образования и его сопоставлению с интеллигентностью, взаимосвязи интеллигентности и образования в различных ситуациях аналитическим случаем, которые дают определение их философской среды. Тем самым определяет аксиологический анализ интеллигентности и образования, специфические особенности двух этих двух терминологий.

В статье рассматриваются понятие интеллигентности и образованности на примере учителя, где он является моделью одного из понятий, но оно ни всегда сочетается со вторым.

Ключевые слова: интеллигенция, образованный человек, интеллектуальная зрелость отношения, этическая среда, консервативный период, школа, учитель.

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Kalit so'zlar: ziyolilar, bilimli inson, intellektual yetuklik, munosabatlar, axloqiy muhit, konservativ davr, maktab, o'qituvchi

Introduction.

Distinguishing importance between an educated person and representatives of the uneducated part of society is an eternal problem of civilizations. It is known that from the ancient periods the attitude towards an educated person was distinguished by special gratitude, respect, recognition of this quality as a special seal of Saint in our country. Elderly people remember the reverent attitude to teachers, to an educated person as an image of a saint. It is impossible not to notice that even in distant times, from the height of today's days perceived as very prosperous, a certain negative attitude towards the intellectual maturity.

As we can see, the Man of Civilization is a true intellectual in the complete meaning of the word. As a self-evident axiomatic truth, it can be repeated that it was, a hundred years ago or in recent period is far from these characteristics, and, unfortunately, it remains relationship between the intelligentsia and the rest of the masses has always been complex. At the same time, as the intelligentsia and the "rest of the masses" tried to look at each other from the height of the greatest snobbery, to see in each other only "uneducated mob" or "highly educated useless people." By the way, the society comes to misunderstanding by analyzing these two terminologies separately giving them sometimes close characteristics and analyze their roles in society as same .

Literature review. Social attitude towards intelligence was not characterized positively and it was highlighted by Sadridin Ayni in the novel "Eski maktab" (An old school). The system education in that period is characterized as conservative period and representative of intelligence - teacher (domla) is presented as evil who has impact in the community..... "Pupils became silent and he took the board under the blank and started to write something on it then showed it my father. My father found some mistakes in teacher's writing and replied: "It should not be written in that way!" the intelligence of my father made me proud of him and feel confidence of his presence . the action of my father made the teacher upset and he asked my dad to correct him. My father did it and comment on his errors....."

The incident occurred in those years when the image of the educated person was held in high esteem. The incident has become a precedent. Apparently, Ayni saw a certain fracture in the public state of mind, fit in disregard for the image and the personality of an intellectual for his main difference from others. First of all, such a difference was his education (we are also talking about human culture). In the future, there were fertile grounds for this in connection with the entry (mainly from an illiterate environment) into the historical arena of the new hegemony. Although it is hardly possible and necessary to blame him for his lack of education...

Abdulla Qodiriy in his story "Quiet job "(Tinch ish) characterizes the teacher Oxun domla with contrast features. And everyone from different age group who will hear his name imagine him in big head cloth (salla) and long gown (chopon). He is Plump . From the right hand sleeve you can see his beads (tasbih) , red round face . The man with his sparse beard is coming. This person was informed enough not only about religion knowledge but also about politics..."

Second characteristics of the teacher depicts us the respect and honor toward the teacher. Abdulla Kodiriy's character is not only educated but also broaden horizon person who was able to keep discussions on different fields with different aged people.

Teachers owning the comprehensions like ability of understanding and accepting the reality, tolerance towards people and the world.

It is necessary to develop intelligence, to train mental strength, as well as physical one. It is important to understand others and self-control is necessary in any condition and situation.

The curriculum of Uzbekistan consists of variety of subjects combining science and humanitarians which require self-confidence of instructors and patience of learners. The idea of education does not convey only idea of information sharing but also implement some comprehensions and skills which can be helpful in reality.

All subject in different educational systems require from learners both education and cognition, the ideas of leadership, tolerance, kindness, politeness which come through context of poems, stories, rules and activities.

The fact is that impoliteness and angry reaction to the environment, rudeness and misunderstanding of others is a sign of mental and spiritual weakness, human inability to live ... Pushing in crowded places is the action of a weak and nervous person, exhausted, reacting incorrectly to everything. Quarreling with neighbors is also a person who does not know how to live who is mentally deaf.

Research Methodology. The ideas of having academic degree is not always indicator of intelligence since it is difficult to understand the persons

The author's character doesn't match the reality of Uzbek intelligence who made the contribution of the Second World War .

Writers and poets of Uzbekistan as Hamid Alimjan, Gafur Ghulam, Mirtemir, Zulfiya, Hamid Ghulam, Turab Tula, Mirmukhsin M.Shiverdin, V.Lipko, A. Kahkhar, S.Somova and many others worked fruitfully during the war, the activities of Uzbek cinema workers were subordinated to the interests of protecting the Motherland , who rebuilt the creative and production processes of making films in the shortest possible time. At the very beginning of the war, a number of short films and feature documentaries were created, mobilizing the people for military and labor exploits. In mid-July 1941, the Tashkent Newsreel Studio released the newsreel "Ordinary Uzbekistan" (No. 26), which vividly and convincingly showed the patriotic mood of the Uzbek people, who swore to work tirelessly for the defense of the Motherland, not sparing their strength, until the final defeat of enemies

Learning about the evolution of the concept in the post-Soviet period, it is necessary to fix the difference in its cultural meanings for ordinary cultural carriers and the intellectual elite. If for the former, the intelligentsia, as sociological surveys show, remains the color of the nation, the conscience of society, uniting in itself the social and ideological criteria, i.e. the tradition of word usage of the 60-80s of the XIX century is largely preserved here , the latter, as already noted, speak of the end of the intelligentsia, that this concept ceases to work in new conditions, since both social and ideological grounds for its use disappear. The resulting gap opens up wide and unpredictable opportunities for further semantic transformations.

Analysis and results. Summing up the analysis, it should be noted that the functional load of the concept of "intelligentsia" and its semantic evolution are determined by two semantic complexes underlying all subsequent transformations.

We find the answer to this question in Likhachev, the philosopher, Likhachev, the thinker, Likhachev is a teacher. "Enrich a truly intelligent person of all his knowledge, education, deprive him of his memory itself. Let him forget everything in the world, will not know the classics of literature, will not remember the greatest works art, will forget the most important historical events, but if at the same time he retains a receptivity to intellectual values, love to acquire knowledge, interest in history, aesthetic flair, will be able to distinguish a real work of art from a crude "thing", made only to surprise, if he can admire the beauty of nature, understand the character and individuality of another person, enter into his position, and understanding the other person, help he will not show rudeness, indifference, malice, envy, but will appreciate the other if he shows respect for the culture of the past, the skills of a well-mannered person, responsibility in solving moral issues, the richness and accuracy of his language – spoken and written - that will be an intelligent person"

Thus, an intellectual is a person of broad independent thinking, a person who produces spiritual values, and on in this field, his activity goes far beyond his, perhaps, narrow profession, speciality and becomes the property of all mankind .

The relationship between the intelligentsia and the rest of the masses has always been complicated. At the same time, how the intelligentsia and the "rest of the mass" tried to look at each other from the height of great snobbery, to see in each other only "uneducated rabble" or "highly educated unnecessary people."

Conclusion/Recommendations

Education is the process of developing skills, knowledge and talents through research, training and experience. Mostly the quality of education is connected with development of characters and somehow serves of the means to show our intelligence efficaciously. The main difference between education and intelligence is that education is personal engagement and utility of their cognitive ability. Intelligence is internal power you are born with and you can choose whether to develop or not. Undoubtedly personal educational achievement is influenced by genetics, while the environmental factor has equal importance.

Educated layer of society are they who are able to stay in educational sectors and absorb information. Some people never finish high school, however others continue to study entire doctorates at university. The level of intelligence in an individual depends on various on various factors, including the genetics, upbringing, environment and approach to educational activity. We are all born with a capability for learning which influenced by IQ or intelligence of our parents.

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2 МАХСУС СОН

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PHILOSOPHY AND LIFE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 2

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